

DIGITALIZATION OF KARAKALPAK LANGUAGE

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Annotation: This article will discuss ideas and considerations for digitizing the Karakalpak language. Digitalization of the Karakalpak language is an important step towards the preservation and promotion of this unique language in the digital age. Karakalpak is a Turkic language spoken by the Karakalpak people of Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan. With the development of technology and the increasing use of digital platforms for communication, it has become important to ensure that minority languages such as Karakalpak are not lagging behind.

Key words: Karakalpak language, digitization, online resources, language learning applications, cultural heritage preservation, public construction, standardization, accessibility, language revitalization, digital publications

One of the main advantages of digitizing the Karakalpak language is the preservation of cultural heritage. By creating digital resources such as online dictionaries, language learning apps, and e-books in Karakalpak, the language can be made more accessible to a wider audience, including the younger generation, who are more used to learning from digital devices and using them in communication. This helps ensure that the language is passed down from generation to generation.

Digitalization also plays an important role in the global promotion of Karakalpak language. With social networking platforms, websites, and mobile apps, Karakalpak speakers can connect with each other, exchange resources, and collaborate on projects to further develop the language. It not only helps to raise awareness of the language, but also instills a sense of community among speakers both locally and internationally.

Moreover, digitalization of Karakalpak language can facilitate its integration into various fields such as education, business and government. By creating digital tools and resources in Karakalpak, it is easier for speakers of the language to access information, communicate effectively, and participate in the digital economy. This, in turn, will help expand the capabilities of the Karakalpak community and promote language diversity in the digital space.

There are also problems with digitizing the Karakalpak language. One of the main problems is the lack of standardized digital resources and tools in the Karakalpak language. The development of these resources requires time, effort, and experience, as well as collaboration between linguists, programmers, and

community members. In addition, problems may arise with the compatibility of blackspot fonts and characters with existing digital platforms, which can prevent the transition to digital formats without problems.

In language acquisition, specifically in Karakalpak language education to what extent is the use of digital tools to the goals and objectives of training it is assumed to study compliance. Socio-economic reforms, education and education, related to the prestige of the Karakalpak language in the country and in the world in regulatory documents "digitization of educational materials in education", "e-learning resources for the preschool, secondary and higher education system further improvement, as well as internal and world educational resources tasks such as "ensuring use" were imposed.

So today in his lessons, only from presentations, electronic forms of textbooks to the methodological support of the teachers using their classes interactive digital resources, namely electronic dictionaries, web quests, multimedia it's time to add assignments and exercises too. Importantly the teacher does not wait for someone to create these resources.

On the contrary, the age, knowledge of students, the degree of mastery of the subject, the pace it is possible to create and use independently, taking into account. The amount of sites in almost 30 years since the creation of the Internet is 2 approaching billion. Among them are educational sites.

In the digital age, several digital resources have been created with the aim of promoting the preservation and use of the Karakalpak language. Some examples include: there are online dictionaries that show translations, definitions and examples of words in Karakalpak language. These dictionaries help Karakalpak speakers to easily search for words and phrases, enhancing their language skills and understanding.

There are mobile apps designed specifically for learning the Karakalpak language. These apps offer users interactive lessons, quizzes, and exercises to practice on the go and improve their language skills. Karakalpak has e-books and digital publications covering a wide range of topics from literature and poetry to history and culture. These sources make it easier for Karakalpak speakers to use their own language reading material.

Online forums and social media groups: there are online forums and social media groups dedicated to the Karakalpak language, where speakers can connect, exchange resources, ask questions, participate in discussions on the language and its application. There are websites that provide information about Karakalpak language, grammar, vocabulary wealth and pronunciation. These

websites serve as a valuable resource for Karakalpak language learners and speakers seeking a deeper understanding of Karakalpak language.

Karakalpak language keyboard apps: there are keyboard apps that allow users to type in Karakalpak language on their mobile devices and computers. These apps make it easier for black-and-white speakers to communicate in their own language through digital platforms. In general, these digital resources play a decisive role in promoting the Karakalpak language, making it more accessible, ensuring its continuous use and development in the digital age.

Digital resources created for the Karakalpak language have been effective in several ways in promoting and maintaining the language:

- Expansion of special capabilities: digital resources have made the Karakalpak language more accessible to a wider audience, including speakers living in remote areas or outside Karakalpakstan. People can now use educational materials, dictionaries and other resources online, which has helped to increase interest in the language.

- Language learning: language learning apps and online courses have made it easier for people to learn Karakalpak at their own pace and comfort. These resources provide interactive lessons, quizzes, and exercises to help students effectively practice and improve their language skills.

- Community building: online forums dedicated to the Karakalpak language and groups on social networks have helped form a sense of community between speakers and learners. People can connect, exchange resources and participate in discussions about language, which has created a favorable environment for language lovers.

- Preservation of cultural heritage: digital publications, e-books and websites in Karakalpak have played a decisive role in preserving the cultural heritage of the language. These sources demonstrate Karakalpak literature, poetry, history and traditions, ensuring that this rich cultural heritage is transmitted to future generations.

- Language standardization: digital resources have also contributed to standardization of the Karakalpak language by ensuring consistent spelling, grammar rules, and vocabulary richness. This helped maintain the integrity of the language and ensure its proper use in digital communication.

In general, digital resources created for the Karakalpak language have been instrumental in promoting and maintaining the language by increasing language usability, facilitating language learning, forming a community of speakers and learners, preserving cultural heritage, and standardizing the language. These

efforts served to ensure the continuous use and development of the Karakalpak language in the digital age.

In conclusion, digitization of blackcurrant is a decisive step towards preserving, promoting and revitalizing this unique language in the digital age. By creating digital resources, developing online communities and integrating the language into different areas, we can ensure the development and development of the Karakalpak language in the modern world. It is necessary to continue to support initiatives aimed at digitizing the Karakalpak language and ensuring its stability for future generations.

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